

E-Shopping - A Changing Shopping Trend - A Review

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Abstract

Paper type – Literature Review

Online shopping is a recent phenomenon in the field of e-commerce and will certainly be the future of shopping in the world. Most companies use their online portals to sell their products / services, although online is very common outside India, with an increase in the Indian market. The main aim of this paper is to review the literature on online shopping for consumer behaviour, and Rising Internet penetration in India. In addition, the paper identified the new developments process of e-commerce in India. Current literature was designed to help predict future directions and trends for consumers in online shopping, as well as analysed the consumer behavior towards online shopping, with the various factors affecting online shopping. It also analyzed the recent growth of online shopping and top online shopping sites in India.

Keywords: Online Shopping, Consumer Behavior, Influencing Factor, Recent & changing Trends, New developments & Top New Shopping Sites.

Introduction

The rapid rate of growth in online transactions is also helpful in boosting the Indian economy. Globally, an increasing number of people are buying through the Internet, because digital marketing is more convenient, a form of direct marketing that connects consumers and sellers electronically using interactive technologies such as Emails, websites, online forums and newsgroups, interactive TV, mobile communications, etc. (Kotler and Armstrong 2009). Consumers can find an item of interest by visiting the retailer’s website directly or by browsing among the best alternative vendors, which will show the same product availability and pricing at different e-retailers. Through 2018, consumers can shop online using a variety of different consumer and industrial products. Online shopping involves a transaction made over the Internet. When we buy a good over the internet, it’s called online shopping, this process is called business-to-consumer (B2C) online shopping. The way of people buy and sell goods and services has changed over the last decade. In addition, people and businesses also purchase a variety of online services, such as a broking service or a job search service.

Definition of Marketing

Philip Kotler defines marketing as —Marketing is about Satisfying needs and wants through an exchange process.

Purpose of Research: The aim of this paper is to understand the concept of online shopping and emerging trends in shopping. Analysed that new developments of India . An attempt has been made through this paper to learn the factors that influence online shopping.

Methodology: This paper is the result of an in-depth study of secondary data sources, such as papers, books, journals and Internet sources.

Online Shopping in India-2019

Increasing sales and demand for quality products to improve consumer spending. India ranked 77th in the 2019 business of the World Bank. (Updated Sept. 2019).The wayof business is done in India has been changed by e-commerce. It is estimated that the Indian e-commerce market will grow from US\$ 38.5 billion in 2017 to US\$ 200 billion by 2026. The industry’s growth has been driven by increased penetration of the Internet and smartphones.The country’s on-going digital transformation is expected to increase India’s total Internet user base from 604.21 million by December 2018 to 829 million by 2021. The Internet economy of India is predicted to double from US\$ 125 billion in April 2017 to US\$ 250 billion by 2020, largely supported by ecommerce. India’s E-commerce revenues are expected to jump from US\$ 39 billion in 2017 to US\$ 120 billion in 2020, growing at an annual rate of 51%, the highest in the world.

Market Size

The Indian e-commerce market is expected to rise to US\$ 200 billion by 2026, powered by increasing smartphone penetration, the introduction of 4G networks and an increase in customer assets. From US\$ 38.5 billion in 2017 Online retail sales in India are expected to increase by 31 per cent to US\$ 32.70 billion by 2017.Headed by Flipkart, Amazon India and Paytm Mall in 2018. During 2018, electronics is currently the largest contributor to online retail sales in India, accounting for 48 per cent, followed closely by clothing at 29 per cent.

Achievements

The Government’s achievements in the last four years are as follows:

- Under the Digital India Movement, the Government launched a number of initiatives such as the Udaan, Umang, India Portal, etc.
- Under the internet saathi project, the Government has influenced more than 16 million Indian women and reached 166,000 villages.

B2B’s online trading network, which links small and medium-sized manufacturers and wholesalers with online retailers and provides them with logistics, payments and technology support, has vendors in over 80 cities in India and delivers to over 500 cities.

- According to the e-governance index, India has increased from 2018 to 2014 by 11 positions to 107 in 2016.
- The government has introduced bharat interface for money (bhim), a simple mobile platform for digital payments.

The e-commerce industry has had a direct impact on micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) in India by providing financing, technology and training and has a positive impact on other industries as well.The Indian e-commerce industry has been on an upward growth path and is expected to surpass the US to become the world’s second-largest e-commerce market by 2034. Technology-enabled innovations such as digital payments hyper-local logistics, analytics-driven

customer engagement and digital advertising are likely to support growth in the sector. Growth in the e-commerce sector will also improve jobs, increase export earnings, increase ex-chequer tax collection and provide better products and services to customers in the long term.

Growth of e-Commerce in India

Notes: Estimated, F- forecasted.

<https://www.ibef.org/industry/ecommerce.aspx>

Increasingly, e-commerce draws consumers from Tier 2 and 3 cities, where people have minimal product exposure but strong ambition.

By 2022, smartphone users are expected to reach 476 million, and by 2026, the e-commerce market is expected to grow by 1200%.

Rising Internet Penetration in India

India's internet penetration rose from just 4% in 2007 to 34.42% in 2017. Recording a 24 per cent CAGR from 2007 to 2017. Total internet penetration in India as of December 2018 was 46.13 million.

Note: Internet penetration- Number of internet subscriber per 100 population.

Source: <https://www.ibef.org/industry/ecommerce.aspx>

List of Top 10 Online Best Shopping Sites in India 2019

Online shopping is slowly slipping into India. As of now, a large number of people prefer to buy everything from grocery stores to online clothing. Not so long ago, Indian viewers were suspicious of online shopping due to potential scams, etc. India has come a long way of being a country of suspicious online shoppers to a nation of millions of happy online shoppers.

1. Flipkart.com

This one has to come down first. The whole country depends entirely on Flipkart for almost all of its shopping needs. From gift vouchers to electronics, it sells everything to home appliances. Statistics actually suggest that there are more items on Flipkart than in a mall. Hence, for all their shopping needs, Indians rely heavily on Flipkart.

2. Amazon.in.

A large number of Indians swear by the Amazon services. Amazon and Flipkart are always at battle with each other and always tight on their feet. Amazon has just as many goods as Flipkart. In reality, Amazon seems to be selling more than Flipkart. Because Amazon is an American company, it lacks the taste of dishes that an Indian would prefer.

3. Candere

Online jewellery shopping is growing in leaps and bounds. Why do you get through all the trouble and go to stores to buy fine jewellery? Candere, Kalyan Jewellers ‘ online concern is where you should go. They have a catalog of 7000 + models, which includes a combination of diamonds, gold and platinum jewellery. Gain exposure to all of these models at your disposal and pay at ease with any price.

4. Jabong.com

Jabong is once again an American company, but seems to be doing very well in India. It’s got a lot of clothes and accessories for sale, and it’s a total heaven for those who enjoy shopping for clothes. It’s got all kinds of products from western wear to desi kurtis, and it would be fun to sit back and shop for Jabong clothes. Women shoppers overly prefer Jabong.

5. Myntra.com

Equally large numbers of women favor Myntra over Jabong. Myntra also has a large number of accessories and clothing on its online portal. It also has a wide number of categories, and one can purchase from a class with their preferences. From western to ethnic to local, all kinds of clothes are sold on Myntra.

6. Localbanya.com

This is a website for shopping grocery stores and is a blessing for working women. It’s also a blessing to a woman who’s busy all the time. All of the items in the grocery store are available here and one can buy them according to their needs. Everything is available here, from organic to inorganic products. Thus, localbanya.com is indeed one of India’s leading shopping malls.

7. Homeshop18

This is an equally popular website for online shoppers. Those who don’t mind waiting for a little longer for delivery at a lower price, order from here. A lot of times, the cheapest things and the most distant items can be found on Homeshop18.com. The page also has an equally large number

of shoppers who are loyalists Homeshop18 cannot, be trusted when one is in an emergency. You’d prefer to buy from one of the websites where they offer express shipments.

8. Infibeam.com

Infibeam.com is a place where you often find things that can’t be found anywhere else. The rarest of items, the rarest of books and the rarest of computers, and many more, are easily found on infibeam.com. Infibeam.com has a long way to go before the ranks get higher, but it’s certainly not doing poorly so far.

9. Shopclues.com

Shopclues is famous for their highly discounted best shopping deals. It is one of the best online shops offering a wide range of cameras, computer accessories, mobile phones, gifts, jewellery, cosmetics, toys, shoes, books and bags.

10. Firstcry.com

Firstcry.com India’s largest children’s store selling 70,000 + items from 400 + top international and Indian brands. First Cry sells nearly all baby care items, such as diapers, toys, shirts, scooters, shoes, and more.

Paytm has launched Paytm Store, which is equivalent to Amazon and Flipkart. You can go and shop at the Paytm Mall. Paytm Mall sells electronic goods, footwear, wallets, home decor, men’s and women’s clothing and many more items that are 100% authentic. When you shop at Paytm Mall, then you get cashbacks, these cashbacks can be used later to process phone recharges, pay bills, and other items.

Factors Influencing Consumer Behaviour Towards Online Shopping

Personal Characteristics

Characteristics of an individual are an important factor in the decision-making process of purchasing. Personal factors include age, race, occupation, income status, education and lifestyle. All age groups are familiar with the use of the Internet.

Psychological Characteristics

Online consumers deal psychologically with themselves and frequently question themselves. Motivation makes consumers wonder whether they should look at a better price, or whether they should shop online more often, and that kind of question. Perception is one of the most important factors and makes customers question the security of the website or the quality of the product. Personal preferences make it possible for consumers to decide. The fourth is attitude, and attitudes can easily change, so many advertisers are interested in these features. Consumers are trying to find out what they like about a particular situation or not. The last variable is emotion; they may find their last experience. Consumers are affected by choices, and emotions change with the experience of their choice.

Social Characteristics

The social impact comes from the comparison classes. For online consumers, reference groups are identified as virtual communities, consisting of web-site discussion groups. Other people’s experiences, opinions have been shown in this medium and have an impact on consumers. The other are contact links, website links related to the product or service, that make it possible for individuals to make decisions. Family is one of these reference groups.

Cultural Characteristics

Different social groups are developing different behaviors. Consumers from the lower social classes would not have the same properties as a higher purchasing intention or higher probability as a higher social class. In addition, culture sets values and beliefs in the early ages, thus, the expectations and needs of an individual are influenced by this defined feature.

Conclusion

E-commerce is form of electronic commerce. It will become a huge industry in the coming years, and online shopping is now becoming a big part of the daily life of customers in order to meet their never-ending requirements in a convenient way. Online shopping is starting to pick up and is becoming a phenomenon. More customers engage in online shopping, as research has shown, due to the value proposition it provides to the customer, such as convenience, 24x7 shopping, door-to-door delivery, a wide range of products and an ever-expanding selection of exclusive and interesting gift ideas, as well as increased consumer interest in online shopping. This study concludes that socio-economic factors have an effect on online shopping, i.e. employment, income level, area of living, etc. Currently, all transactions are cashless and also affect the growth of online shopping. Online shopping is also generating a desire to buy, as well as the services provided by the online shopping website make good customer relations and after-sales services. There is no question that in the future, all goods and services will be readily available on different websites with great services and deals to draw more and more customers.

References

1. Prof. Hrishikesh M. Bhagat (2015), “International Journal in Management and Social Science”, Vol.03 Issue-08, (August) ISSN: 2321-1784.
2. Dr. Charu Bisaria (2016), “International Journal in Management and Social Science”, Vol.04 Issue-05 May ISSN: 2321-1784.
3. Radapaka Vijaya (2016), “International Journal in Management and Social Science”, Vol.04 Issue-06, June. ISSN: 2321-1784.
4. Dr. V. Santhi & Dr. L. NandaGopal (2018), “International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics”, Volume 120 No. 5, ISSN 1459-1489, ISSN 1314-3395 (on-line version).
5. S. Gowthami & S. Loganayaki (2018), “International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education (IJMRME)”, Volume 4, Issue 2, ISSN (Online): 2454 – 6119.
6. Dr.N.Gunasekaran & Mrs.A.Ramya (2018), “Shanlax International Journal of Commerce”, vol. 6, no. S1, pp. 126–132.
7. D.Melbha. (2018). “International Journal of Research – Granthaalayah”, 6(5), September. P.no. 326-333.
8. E- Commerce Third Edition- Elias M. Awad.
9. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1283415>
10. <https://www.bloggersideas.com/top-10-online-shopping-sites-in-india-best-shopping-sites-india/>
11. <https://www.ibef.org/industry/ecommerce.aspx>